

Beaming Power: Photovoltaic Laser Power Converters for Power-by-Light

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Context & Scale

The transmission of power using light instead of electricity –the so called *power-by-light (PBL)*– has been around for some decades now. Despite this long history, it has been only in recent years when PBL systems have experienced enormous effervescence in situations where the direct use of electrical energy to power electronic equipment is either not possible or not recommendable. PBL systems are the smarter solution for monitoring and controlling processes under strict safety conditions in contexts with high fire or explosion risk (refineries, mines, fuel tanks in space and aircrafts), or that need galvanic insulation (high voltage power lines, lighting-safe monitoring, medical applications), etc. The core of a PBL system is the photovoltaic laser power converter (PVLPC) which transforms the laser light delivered through an optical fibre into electricity. Recently, a PVLPC has demonstrated the highest efficiency for any photovoltaic converter, i.e. 68.9% at a laser illumination of 858 nm.

This review begins with a brief overview of the functionalities of PBL systems and the critical requirements imposed to PVLPCs. Afterwards, the history of PVLPCs is revisited, including the recent hatching of companies and technical conferences in the field. A detailed comparison amid the different typologies of PVLPCs is tackled in terms of their efficiency, delivered power, voltage, temperature effects and manufacturability, highlighting their advantages and disadvantages depending on the application. We also pinpoint the main aspects limiting the efficiency of PVLPCs and the ways to circumvent them. Advanced concepts such as photon recycling, high performance back reflectors, luminescent coupling, etc. and their potential to improve the PVLPC performance are discussed. Future PVLPCs must exhibit higher efficiencies and delivered power, robustness at rough environmental conditions and lower manufacturing cost. This review aims at showing the routes to achieve these goals.

SUMMARY

PhotoVoltaic Laser Power Converters (PVLPCs) currently exhibit the highest photovoltaic efficiency, i.e. 68.9% at a laser illumination of 858 nm. They are the core element of Power-by-Light (PBL) systems which basically made up of a power laser, an optical fibre and a PVLPC. PBL allows the safe transfer of power in situations where the direct use of electrical energy to power electronic equipment is either not possible or not recommendable. There is a huge market for PBL systems, for example in applications needing to monitor and control processes under strict safety conditions because of a high fire or explosion risk (refineries, mines, fuel tanks in space and aircrafts, etc.), the possible malfunction of sensitive electrical equipment in areas of high electromagnetic noise (nuclear plants), the need of galvanic insulation (high voltage power lines and lighting-safe monitoring), etc. The first PBL system was built in 1978 but it has been only recently when PBL systems are having an outburst with continuous efficiency improvements, creation of start-ups, big companies entering the business, and increasing number of scientific publications and specialized technical conferences. This review begins with an overview of the functionalities of PBL systems and the critical requirements imposed to PVLPCs. Afterwards, a brief outlook on the history of PVLPCs is presented. A detailed comparison among the different typologies of PVLPCs in terms of efficiency, delivered power, voltage, temperature effects and manufacturability is carried out, highlighting their advantages and disadvantages depending on the application. We also point out the main aspects limiting the efficiency of PVLPCs and possible ways to circumvent them. Finally, we discuss the perspectives of PVLPCs together with the possible routes to a steady deployment of PBL systems to serve a considerable number of applications in our daily life

INTRODUCTION

There are many situations in which the direct use of electrical energy to power electronic equipment is either not possible or not recommendable. Areas with these restrictions are generally called “exclusion regions”¹ and exist in applications needing to monitor and control processes under strict safety conditions because of a high fire or explosion risk (refineries, mines, fuel tanks in space and aircrafts, etc.), the possible malfunction of sensitive electrical equipment in areas of high electromagnetic noise (nuclear plants), the need of galvanic insulation (high voltage lines and lighting-safe monitoring), etc.^{2,3,4,5,6}. Alternative fields of application lie in the remote powering of rechargeable batteries (medical applications),⁷ presence or flame detectors,⁸ rotating systems and even for powering satellites during periods of eclipse or Moon bases from Earth in the Moon night.^{9,10,11}

Optical power transfer, or power-by-light (PBL in the following), is an alternative technology which provides a smart solution in these special situations. The reason why PBL systems ensure safety in these applications is the achievement of galvanic insulation in the *exclusion region*. Both optical fibre based and wireless systems provide the power link with immunity from electromagnetic noise and interference (EMI) and electrical insulation between both ends of the link. Therefore, the danger of fire or explosions is almost inexistent because of the absence of sparks in these systems. A PBL system is made up of a light source, a transmission medium and a light receiver.¹² The light source converts the electrical power taken from a non-problematic region into optical power, which is sent by means of the transmission medium to the light receiver which transforms the light power into electricity and powers the electronic equipment inside the exclusion region.

There are essentially two options for the transmission medium in a PBL system, namely systems using optical fibre links, and systems transmitting the optical power through free space or the atmosphere (wireless systems). The inherent difficulties of wireless systems have reduced their use to just a few research projects and always for low power levels. Such difficulties include the need of a permanent and precise pointing between light emitter and receiver, the variable attenuation (i.e. losses) of optical beams travelling through the atmosphere, the need of light beam protection against the interposition of some external influence and safety concerns for the human eye, among others. Therefore, wireless systems will not be further considered in this review.

In optical fibre links, the light is guided through an optical fibre from the light source to the optical receiver taking advantage of the electrical insulation between fibre ends and their immunity to electromagnetic noise and interference. Due to the special features of optical fibre based PBL applications, the properties of the components making up these systems are quite different from those commonly used in optical fibre data communications systems. The latter are large bandwidth and low power systems, while in PBL links the transmitted power is usually much higher whereas the system bandwidth is not important. In some cases, the same fibre transmits data at a specific wavelength and carries power using a different wavelength, which is generally called a share scenario,^{13,14} which has a trade-off to meet the specifications of both applications simultaneously with a special attention to the high power laser¹⁵ and the potential appearance of non-linear effects in the optical fibre.¹⁶

Optical data systems use high quality lasers, which exhibit very narrow monochromatic and highly coherent emission. The laser wavelength must also correspond to the second or third communication windows of the optical fibre (centred at 1.3 and 1.55 microns, approximately, see Figure 1, bottom left), where attenuation and dispersion are very low, which is key because of the long distances covered by these links (hundred or thousand kilometres). Light receivers commonly used in optical fibre data systems are photodiodes¹⁷ because these devices can receive low power signals at a very high transmission rate. However, data receivers cannot convert efficiently high optical power levels, because they saturate. Therefore, photovoltaic converters are the suitable optical receivers in PBL systems. These devices can exhibit efficiencies over 60 % at high input monochromatic optical power and they do not need any kind of biasing.¹⁸ On the other hand, power transmission via optical fibres is, in most cases, carried out over much shorter distances than those of optical communication systems. Therefore, low attenuation requirements are less stringent than for data transmission applications. Accordingly, the transmission wavelength can lie in the first optical communication window (800-900 nm, see Figure 1-bottom left), where low-cost and high-power laser diodes are available.

The sketch of an optical fibre PBL system is shown in Figure 1. In most applications, it is important to monitor the remote node in the exclusion region, knowing ambient parameters such as temperature or humidity, checking the optical power delivered and saving any surplus energy for future usage by charging a battery⁸. In other applications, to improve the energy efficiency of the overall system, there is a control of the power emitted by the laser depending on the requirements of the load.¹⁹ For all those applications, there is a communication link^{8,19,20} either unidirectional or bidirectional, between the base station and the exclusion region. As shown in Fig. 1, there can be a dedicated optical fibre for optical powering and another fibre or a bundle of fibres as the communication link. The optical fibres can simultaneously propagate different

signals by using wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) or use different wavelengths for the downlink (from base station to remote station) and uplink (from remote station to base station).

All the components and subsystems of the PBL system of Figure 1 are off-the-shelf products with a wide commercial availability which is not the case for the PhotoVoltaic Laser Power Converter (PVLPC, from now on). A PVLPC is the core of the PBL system on which the global efficiency of the system mainly depends. The PVLPC has to efficiently convert the laser light exiting the optical fibre with challenging features such as a power density reaching several W/cm^2 , Gaussian irradiance profile, wide angular distribution, circular symmetry, etc. In addition, the PVLPC has to properly manage the heating produced in the conversion process of the laser light, withstand operation temperatures from several tens of degrees below zero to well over $100^\circ C$ (depending on the application), to behave reliably under extreme environments and all this at an acceptable cost. Accordingly, this review is focused on PVLPCs whose successful development will determine a wide deployment of PBL systems

Figure 1. Sketch of a PBL system

The optical power is sent through a dedicated optical fibre while the data are transmitted (mono or bidirectionally) by a different optical fibre. In an alternative scheme, both optical power and data can be sent through the same optical fibre by using multiplexing techniques. The core element is the PVLPC (in red font). A photograph of a real PVLPC, including the emulation of an impinging misaligned laser beam (in red) to emphasize a possible power loss problem and with a non-uniform irradiance, is presented on top. Optical fibre windows (hatched columns) as a function of wavelength and the mechanisms responsible of attenuation are presented in the bottom left figure. Typical laser wavelengths for each transmission window are also depicted in the graph.

Fibre optic PBL systems have been used since 1978 when an optically powered sound alerter was demonstrated by DeLoach et al for a fibre-based telephone network.²¹ From then many papers describing a multitude of PBL systems have been published.^{22,23,24} Despite this long history, it has been only in recent years when PBL systems have experienced enormous effervescence and have been successfully applied to a multitude of settings.^{19,25,26,27,28} The opportunities and market applications are huge for the three optical fibre transmission windows. This deployment relies on the technological development of the core component, i.e.

the PVLPC made of different semiconductors to optimize their response at different laser wavelengths. PVLPCs for the first transmission window, because of their current maturity^{29,30,31} in comparison with those for the second and third windows, constitute the cornerstone in current technological developments. Therefore, in this work we present a review mostly focused on PVLPCs for the first transmission window, which are the key to open a constellation of new avenues for PBL systems.

PVLPC Basics and History

PVLPCs must meet the following requirements to enable the efficient operation of real PBL systems:

- Bandgap of the PVPLC semiconductor absorber must be matched to the laser wavelength.
- Output voltage and power: high enough for the target application. The PVLPC must supply the voltage needed by the remote station (Figure 1). If not, an additional electronic circuit (namely a DC/DC converter) shall be used. Even though a PVLPC might deliver the required voltage, there will be different load conditions in a PBL system, so DC-DC converters with Maximum Power Point Controller (MPPC) could be required to adjust the electrical output power of PVLPCs to the load.³² There is a minimum required voltage at the DC-DC input, which might not be supplied by a single PV converter. For input values below 0.8 V, it might be impossible to use a voltage booster. Efficient DC-DC converters include inductances in the circuit, which need a start-up current substantially higher than that required in a normal operation. Therefore, the PVLPC must be dimensioned in order to ensure this maximum power consumption in the transient period.
- Efficiency. Even supplying enough power and voltage, in many applications it may be important to achieve a specific power transmission efficiency for the whole PBL system which is mainly governed by the efficiency of the PVLPC.
- Size and geometry fitted to the laser spot depending on the numerical aperture of the optical fibres, to obtain an efficient coupling of the optical power to the PVLPC.
- Operational Capabilities to cover the different applications and environments:
 - Proper packaging with standard fibre connectors such as SMA (SubMiniature version A), FC (Fibre optic Connector) or E2000 among others, able to withstand the required power levels. It is also recommendable to use a proper heatsink when managing high laser powers to avoid the overheating of the PVLPC.
 - Satisfactory operating life.
 - Endurance to the specific environmental and application conditions.
 - Fulfilment of the specific application requirements, such as weight, price, etc.

We anticipate that PVLPCs for the first optical transmission window are based on GaAs from which photovoltaic devices exhibit typical voltages around 1 V. Higher output voltages can be obtained by series interconnecting several photovoltaic converters (Multiple PVLPC, in the following, M-PVLPCs) or by the addition of an external electronic circuit, typically a DC-DC boost converter. The number of converters is chosen according to the desired output voltage. The series connection of single PV converters can be carried out externally by means of wires or tabs.³³ However, in high performance systems, the best alternative is a monolithic interconnection.

Three main different approaches have been described in the literature for PVLPCs: Single Photovoltaic Laser Power Converters (S-PVLPCs), Horizontally interconnected Multiple PVLPC

(HM-PVLPCs) also known as multi-segment converters, and Vertically interconnected Multiple PVLPC (VM-PVLPCs). The different configurations of PVLPCs together with their main features are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Typology and features of PVLPCs

Configuration	Sketch	Advantages	Drawbacks	References.
Single PV Laser Power Converter (S-PVLPC) ^a		Simple and cheap to manufacture High inherent efficiency Low mismatch / spillage losses Low sensitivity to temperature	Produce low voltage Need for a voltage booster, with high start-up current Lower overall system efficiency than multiple PV converters	18,34,35,36,37,38
Horizontally Interconnected Multiple PV Laser Power Converter (HM-PVLPC) ^{b, d}		Medium voltages reachable (<10V) Suitable size and geometry for optical fibre systems Low sensitivity to temperature	Difficult / expensive to manufacture Active area lost in insulation trenches and interconnects High non-uniform illumination losses	29,30,39,40,23,
Vertically Interconnected Multiple PV Laser Power Converter (VM-PVLPC) ^{c, d}		High nominal efficiency Very high voltages reachable (>10V) Suitable size and geometry for optical fibre systems Low mismatch losses / spillage losses Easy post-growth processing	Difficult / expensive crystal growth High sensitivity to temperature	27,31,41,42,43

Note: The figures included are simplified representations of each type of PVLPC. For more details, check the corresponding section of the review. For example, segment interconnections in HM-PVLPCs have been omitted for the sake of picture clarity. So have been tunnel junction interconnects between subcells in VM-PVLPCs.

^a A single junction solar cell is optimized for the conversion of the quasi-monochromatic laser light.

^b A mini PV module is formed by the segmentation of a single junction solar cell grown on a semi-insulating substrate. Segments have the same area (i.e. same current) and are interconnected in series to produce a higher voltage.

^c Different subcells of the same material are grown monolithically and interconnected in series using tunnel junctions (not shown in the sketch). Current matching is attained by modulating the thickness of each subcell.

^d HM-PVLPCs and VM-PVLPCs can be combined into the so called *Hybrid Interconnected Multiple PV Laser Power Converter*⁴⁴, in an attempt to benefit from their respective advantages while minimizing their drawbacks, linked to the number of segments or subcells. In this configuration, an HM-PVLPC with few segments is defined, each segment being a VM-PVLPC with also a limited number of junctions.

A solar cell is a type of photovoltaic converter specifically designed for transforming solar radiation. Historically, solar cells were developed first and thanks to their achieved performance, non-solar new applications such as the PBL were envisioned.⁴⁵ In the early 1970s, AlGaAs-GaAs solar cells had surpassed the efficiency of silicon ones^{46,47} and because of the good pairing of GaAs bandgap to the first transmission window, the first PVLPCs were developed and measured under 800⁴⁸ and 850³⁴ nm laser light. From then, the experience in developing GaAs-based solar cells has been directly applicable to the development of GaAs PVLPCs. However, the PVLPC has

to be adapted and optimized in order to efficiently convert the monochromatic radiation emitted by a laser down to an optical fibre. This optimization includes the following aspects:

- Geometry and size adapted to the application requirements in such a way that they allow a homogeneous distribution of the light on the converter surface, efficient heat management and simple packaging.
- Device configuration to achieve the series-connection of subcells allowing the required output voltage.
- Antireflective coating materials and thicknesses adapted to maximize the light transmission at the laser wavelength.
- Optimization of the semiconductor structure for an optimum performance under the light spectrum and optical power density impinging the PVLPC.
- Front grid developed for the particular irradiance conditions, especially the power density and the Gaussian irradiance profile of the laser beam impinging the converter surface.

Since an increasing output power is demanded to PBL systems, several of these optimization aspects are not very different to those faced in concentrator III-V solar cells⁴⁹ which have achieved very high efficiencies at concentrations around a thousand suns (100 W/cm^2). These irradiance levels are very similar to those received by PVLPCs in PBL systems. Accordingly, the historic evolution of PVLPCs has been closely linked to the development of III-V concentrator solar cells. Figure 2 summarizes the main PVLPC achievements in the last 40 years. A significant efficiency rise has taken place in this century after a stagnant period covering the last 20 years of 20th century. Several reputed research centres, universities and government agencies such as the Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy (Germany), Solar Energy Institute-Technical University of Madrid (Spain), University of Ottawa and University of Sherbrook (Canada), Ioffe Institute of St. Petersburg (Russia), NASA (USA), Sandia National Labs (USA), among others, have contributed to the experimental and theoretical development of PVPLCs for years. More recently, the National Renewable Energy Laboratory, NREL (USA), who currently holds the world record efficiency on solar cells (47.1%), has announced its involvement in PVLPC R&D. From the beginning, companies devoted to III- V multijunction solar cells offered PVLPCs and currently Spectrolab and Azur Space also include PVLPCs in their portfolios. The first company devoted specifically to PVLPCs and PBL systems was Photonic Power Systems created in 1992. As of 2005, when the company was absorbed by JDS Uniphase, it had sold just around 10,000 PVLPCs.⁵⁰ The situation is rapidly evolving and start-ups such as Azastra Opto were created specifically for the PVLPC business. Most importantly, in 2018 Azastra Opto was acquired by Broadcom Ltd. confirming that the PVLPC technology has gained recognition and backing from a major semiconductor company. In parallel, technical conferences with the focus on PVLPCs and PBL systems, such as the international Optical Wireless and Fibre Power Transmission Conference (OWPT), have been launched in 2019 on an annual basis, increasing the number of attendees year after year. All these facts compose an outlook of the present effervescence of PVLPCs for PBL systems in a wide variety of applications and environments with a bright future and increasing market.

Figure 2. History of PVLPCs for the first transmission window

Peak efficiencies of different typologies of PVLPCs are represented inside the timeline. Note the vertical efficiency scale inside the timeline. Moreover, several key results such as elevated power, voltage, etc. are presented with dotted circular lines. References to these results are in the bottom part of the circles. On top and bottom of the timeline the creation of companies devoted to PVLPCs and PBL systems are presented. Relevant results of PBL systems are shown in pink circles at the bottom.

SINGLE PHOTOVOLTAIC LASER POWER CONVERTERS (S-PVLPCs)

S-PVLPCs are III-V single junction solar cells optimized for their operation under monochromatic light.⁵¹ The simplicity of their structure in comparison with M-PVLPCs (see Table 1) allow to use them as benchmark for the development of new technological developments. In fact, the recent efficiency record of 68.9% has been achieved by a S-PVLPC.

A PBL system using a S-PVLPC requires a DC-DC converter^{52,53,54} with typical efficiencies higher than 80%. However, the overall S-PVLPC/DC-DC efficiency is lower than that obtained by M-PVLPCs. Furthermore, the generation of high photocurrents by S-PVLPCs make these devices more sensitive to series resistance losses. These limitations do not make the use of S-PVLPCs recommendable in many real PBL systems.

Many advances in the comprehension of photovoltaic conversion of monochromatic light have been done with S-PVLPCs. This trend is expected to continue in the future. Accordingly, the next subsections analyse the most significant features of S-PVLPCs and their similitudes and differences with single junction solar cells.

Absorber material and laser wavelength

The material choice is determined by the incident laser light.⁵⁵ There is a compromise between the bandgap of the PVLPC and the laser wavelength. GaAs is the most important material used in PVLPCs since its bandgap (1.4 eV or its equivalent bandgap wavelength, 880 nm) matches well the wavelength range of the first transmission window (see Figure 1-bottom left). GaAs bandgap permits the conversion of laser wavelengths from 750 nm to 870 nm with efficiencies close to the theoretical limit, featuring internal luminescence efficiencies (η_{int} , i.e. radiative to non-radiative recombination ratio) approaching 1.^{21,27} However, effects as thermalization or the decrease in the absorption coefficient can produce efficiency losses at these wavelengths.⁵⁶

Using a monochromatic illumination reduces the impact of carrier thermalization, as compared to solar cells. If a laser with a matched light wavelength to the region of high quantum efficiency

is used, then the S-PVLPCs can provide higher efficiencies than solar cells designed to convert the whole solar spectrum. Even so, depending on the material of the S-PVLPC and laser wavelength used, thermalization can occur if bandgap and laser wavelength do not exactly match. On the other hand, the absorption coefficient of the S-PVLPC semiconductor material decreases significantly as its bandgap is approached. As a consequence of this trade-off, it is recommendable that the energy difference between the laser wavelength and the wavelength of the S-PVLPCs QE peak (which is several nm lower than that of bandgap) is as small as possible.

For example, when using an 808 nm laser, which is the most widely used laser wavelength due to its availability and low cost,⁵⁷ the best option would be to use S-PVLPCs materials with a higher bandgap than GaAs such as AlGaAs. In this manner, thermalization effects would be reduced due to the lower difference between AlGaAs bandgap and 808 nm wavelength. When GaAs is selected as the S-PVLPCs material, it would be more favourable to use lower energy photons, i.e., higher laser wavelengths such as 860 nm.

However, even if thermalization was reduced with these combinations, it is important to consider the typical reduction of the absorption coefficient of the material as the bandgap energy is approached, so the S-PVLPCs would require thicker absorber layers which can impact the carrier collection efficiency, lower the open circuit voltage and increase the manufacturing cost. All things considered, 830-860 nm is the most favourable wavelength for GaAs since it achieves a balance between low thermalization losses and a high absorption coefficient, as different authors have stated.^{51,56,58}

Open-circuit voltage and efficiency

Neglecting series resistance effects, the highest efficiency achievable in a GaAs S-PVLPCs with an ideal internal radiative efficiency (radiative limit) depends, first on the laser wavelength and the input power. Figure 3-a illustrates this case for a GaAs S-PVLPC with 5 μm thick absorber. The closer the wavelength to the bandgap of GaAs, the lower the carrier thermalization losses and the higher the efficiency. However, for a constant absorber thickness, as the bandgap of GaAs is approached and the absorption coefficient decreases, the photocurrent starts to decrease, affecting the efficiency (solid lines in Figure 3). Of course, as the input power density increases, the efficiency increases too in the absence of series resistance effect, due to the higher V_{oc} . In addition to the wavelength and input power, photon recycling⁵⁹ can have a large impact on the efficiency; even more so considering the high internal radiative efficiencies experimentally achieved in GaAs. Placing a back reflector behind the GaAs absorber enhances the photon recycling and V_{oc} , increasing the efficiency. Moreover, the reflector increases the optical path of photons, boosting the light absorption and delaying the efficiency drop towards laser wavelengths closer to the bandgap of GaAs. The dashed lines in Figure 3-a correspond to this case: the boost in photon recycling by the back reflector produces a large efficiency increase observed for all the wavelengths range.

Figure 3. Efficiency vs photon wavelength and input power density and influence of series resistance on the design

Figure a): Calculated efficiency of a single-junction GaAs S-PVLPCs with a 5 μm thick absorber in the radiative limit and no series resistance effects. The solid lines correspond to power converters on GaAs substrates (limited photon recycling) and the dashed lines to power converters with a gold reflector placed behind the absorber (enhanced photon recycling). Figure b): efficiency of GaAs S-PVLPC with experimental spectral response and recombination,³⁸ including series resistance effects using an inverted square front grid with 3 μm wide fingers, emitter sheet resistance of 50 Ω/\square , metal sheet resistance of 0.02 Ω/\square and metal/semiconductor contact resistivity of $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ $\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$. The results are plotted vs the device active area and the input power, and the front grid (number of fingers) is optimized at each point to maximize the efficiency. The dashed lines in this contour plot represent the input power density in W/cm^2 .

Series resistance

The effect of series resistance is one of the major limitations to achieve high efficiencies in single PVLPCs operating at high input powers. In a PVLPC the input and output power are normally a design requirement defined by the application. As compared to solar cells, for a set output power, the larger the PVLPC active area, the lower the input light power density or irradiance. This means that increasing the active area size when is totally illuminated by the available laser beam does not increase the total current and decreases the current density, with direct implications on the effect of series resistance. Figure 3-b illustrates the effect of the input power and device area on the efficiency of GaAs S-PVLPCs. The effect of the V_{oc} on the efficiency dominates at low input powers: the larger the area, the lower the current density and hence the lower the V_{oc} . Thus, the optimum efficiency is achieved for the smallest devices considered. For high input powers, the series resistance effects dominate. The optimum in this case is no longer the smallest device area, since the current density (dashed lines) is high enough as to require denser front grids with higher shadow losses. In fact, in the design of the PVLPC the reliability of the device has to be considered, which can be compromised if excessively high input power densities are used. The maximum efficiency achieved were by using devices of 0.01-0.08 cm^2 .^{35,37}

A common approach to reduce the series resistance is the inclusion of a top lateral conduction layer (LCL), which needs to be highly doped and transparent to the laser wavelength. Thereby, the emitter can be kept thin, thus allowing a high minority carrier collection efficiency, while series resistance is reduced.⁶⁰ AlGaAs^{18,34,37,58,60} and GaInP^{36,61,62} are the two materials typically used as window layer for GaAs junctions. In concentration solar cells, small thicknesses, below 50 nm, are used in the window layer to maximize the light transmission to the absorber layers. High doping levels are used at the same time so that the window layer can contribute to the

lateral spreading of the current.⁶³ Window layers of PVLPCs have the same function but they operate with a single wavelength of the impinging light which allows to use thick GaInP and AlGaAs layers exhibiting a total transparency to the laser light, and decisively helping in the lateral spreading of the current.^{60,64}

Temperature effects

The operating temperature in S-PVLPCs applications typically ranges from -60°C to 100°C,⁵⁶ which can cause the converter to work under not optimal conditions. This especially affects M-PVLPCs based on subcell series-connection due to mismatch effects⁶² but temperature also impacts the S-PVLPCs efficiency. Increasing the temperature of the PVLPC implies a reduction in the bandgap of the material. In consequence, the efficiency decreases due to the reduction of V_{oc} . An approach explored by some authors is using a laser wavelength that takes into account the heating of the PVLPC under operating conditions so that an optimized matching between the laser wavelength and the actual bandgap of the absorber is achieved⁵⁶.

Manufacturing process

The manufacturing process of S-PVLPCs and III-V concentrator solar cells is quite similar. The first PVLPCs were manufactured by Liquid Phase Epitaxy (LPE).³⁴ Currently, metal-organic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) reactors dominate the manufacture of the semiconductor structure of S-PVLPCs which is grown on GaAs wafers.^{36,60}

Once the semiconductor structure is manufactured, metal contacts are applied. The front metal grid is formed by conventional photolithography and etching techniques.³⁴ After that, antireflective coating stacks as MgF_2/ZnS^{58} , MgF_2/TaO_x^{60} or TiO_2/SiO_2^{61} are usually added to minimize reflection losses. The size of S-PVLPCs varies typically from 0.01 cm² to 0.1 cm². In the most efficient PVLPC,³⁸ a back reflector formed by a combined dielectric-metal stack of $MgF_2/AlO_x/Ag$.

Finally, the S-PVLPCs dies have to be encapsulated so that the optical fibre is correctly coupled and aligned to them, leaving an optimal distance between both. The most suitable fibre connectors are HP-SMA (High Power SubMiniature version A) and FC-PC (Fiber Channel-Physical Contact). FC-PC implies lower losses and handles well up to 1.5 W laser power. HP-SMA is more suitable for higher powers even though it produces higher losses. Current commercial PBL systems and HPLs also use E2000 connectors. These connectors can be adapted to different packages in which the manufactured converters are mounted. It is necessary to wire bond the top contact and, depending on the package type, the back contact could be made by wire bonding or by the direct contact between a conductive material and the device.

Despite the theoretical monochromatic efficiency limit of a GaAs-based S-PVLPC is around 80% as we have seen above and in agreement with other works,^{36,60} considerably lower efficiencies (around 60%) are expected when practical losses resulting from reflection, recombination, series resistance and non-idealities of the manufacturing process are taken into account.⁶⁰

The most significant improvements from the first efficiency of these devices published by Merz³⁴ in 1977 with a 46% at 0.5 W/cm² input power density to the current record efficiency achieved by Helmers³⁸ et al with a 68.9 % at 11.4 W/cm² are detailed in Table 2.

Efficiency	Year	Input power density (W/cm ²)	Wavelength (nm)	Improvements	References
46.0 %	1977	0.5	850	First PVLPC	34
52.1 %	1991	0.1	806	Al _{0.3} Ga _{0.7} As reflector	35
54.0 %	2008	36.5	810	Al _{0.5} Ga _{0.45} In _{0.5} As as lateral conduction layer	60
58.3 %	2018	6.8	808	Al _{0.07} Ga _{0.93} As instead of GaAs as active layer	64
68.9%	2021	11.4	858	Dielectric-silver back reflector	38

HORIZONTAL INTERCONNECTED MULTIPLE PHOTOVOLTAIC LASER POWER CONVERTER (HM-PVLPC)

As depicted in Figure 4, in these monolithic series connected devices, several PV converters (subcells) are manufactured on a common substrate and then interconnected forming a sort of mini-PV module.^{41,65,66,67,68} We call them Horizontal Interconnected M-PVLPC, or HM-PVLPCs. In order to have electrically independent segments, the most usual approach is to use a semi-insulating (SI) semiconductor substrate; the active layers lay on such SI substrate, thus being necessary to define both the positive and negative contacts on the front side of the device. As shown in Figure 4, trenches are created in the semiconductor structure to provide electrical insulation between subcells and then they are series-connected by means of a metal bus interconnecting scheme. A dielectric barrier is used to avoid short circuits in the active semiconductor layers, at the *pn* junction. A lateral conduction layer (LCL) is usually included to reduce the series resistance beneath the active layers for high power applications.

Figure 4: Front view and cross-section of a HM-PVLPC

Several pie-shaped subcells are manufactured on a common semi-insulating substrate and series-connected by means of a metal interconnection. A dielectric layer avoids short circuits in the active layers. A lateral conduction layer (LCL) is included in order to reduce the series resistance beneath the active layers. Picture of a four segment HM-PVLPC (left) and cross section of the structure in one of the segments (right).

The monolithic connection on SI substrates has the following advantages regarding the external connection of several PVLPCs: a) minimization of the interconnection series resistance between the subcells carried out by using metal paths; b) reduction in manufacturing mismatch losses since the subcells are formed on the same semiconductor structure⁶⁹; c) simple and efficient thermal control because HM-PVLPCs can be directly attached to a heat sink thanks to the proper electrical insulation allowed by the SI substrate; d) size and weight reduction.

Pie-shaped circular HM-PVLPCs are the most usual approach for PBL systems since the light exiting the optical fibre has circular symmetry. Besides, the interconnection between the subcells is located in the outer area of the device (see Figure 4 left), which makes feasible to illuminate only the active area inside this busbar, minimising the shadowing losses.

When medium to high voltages are required, efficient pie-shaped HM-PVLPCs are not recommendable, because the high number of subcells required produces unacceptable optical losses at the insulation trenches.⁶⁶ Besides, a higher number of subcells make HM-PVLPCs more sensitive to misalignment with the laser spot that produces an inhomogeneous light distribution on each segment. As a rule of thumb we could say that HM-PVLPCs with up to 10-12 subcells can be manufactured, providing both high efficiency and high enough voltage for most applications.

Semiconductor materials

Different III-V materials have been used for HM-PVLPCs. In most cases, they are manufactured using GaAs for the *pn* junction. The most significant difference regarding S-PVLPC is the need of using a SI GaAs substrate to provide electrical insulation among the subcells of a HM-PVLPC in comparison with the conductive GaAs substrate required in S-PVLPC. The rest of the semiconductor structure, namely window and BSF layers can be made of AlGaAs or GaInP for both HM-PVLPC and S-PVLPC. Finally, the use of a thick rear GaAs LCL is highly recommendable in HM-PVLPCs while optional in S-PVLPCs.

Impact of the number of subcells on series resistance and efficiency

The design of HM-PVLPCs, which is thoroughly described in reference ⁶⁶, is more complicated than that of S-PVLPCs. Since the current must flow laterally in the base and in the LCL, the series resistance associated to these layers has a significant impact.³⁰ Consequently, in order to limit this series resistance, the device size must be kept reduced. However, this has the drawback of increasing the optical losses in the insulation trenches which exhibit a minimum width (dependent on the photolithographic and etching processes). So, the smaller the size of the device the higher the percentage of light lost at the insulation trenches. Therefore, the device size must be chosen in order to reach a trade-off between low series resistance (for which a small size is recommended) and low insulation trench losses (for which a larger size is better). Accordingly, the calculation of the efficiency must take into account these inherent aspects derived for the geometry and typology of HM-PVLPCs. Figure 5a shows the relationship between optical losses of the insulation trenches expressed in terms of the ratio between the area of illumination trenches to the total device active area, that we call Insulation Trench Factor (ITF), and total series resistance, r_s , as a function of the incoming laser light power density (830 nm) for HM-PVLPCs with a number of subcells, n , of 2, 3, 4, 6 and 12. Each point of the curves corresponds to the optimum structure calculated for each laser power density. The results show

that, as the incoming light power increases, the series resistance must be reduced, which can be done by reducing the device size but this increases the ITF optical losses.

Figure 5: Several losses and performance as a function laser power density

a) Total series resistance and insulation trench optical losses factor (ITF) as a function of the incoming laser power density (830 nm). Each point of the lines corresponds to a different optimum semiconductor structure calculated at each power density. b) Optimum area as a function of incoming power density. The number of subcells, n , has been fixed to 2, 3, 4, 6 and 12. Each point corresponds to a different optimum structure for each incoming power density. c) Efficiency for $n=2, 4, 6, 12$ as a function of the d/D_0 ratio and θ (see the inset). The structures considered are those which lead to the maximum efficiencies with no misalignment, for each n . The laser power density ranges from 2 to 20 W/cm^2 . Laser beam diameter is the same as that of the device inside busbar.

Figure 5b shows the HM-PVLPC optimum area as a function of the incoming laser power density (830 nm). Each point corresponds to a different optimum semiconductor structure. It can be seen that, in all cases, the optimum device area decreases as power density increases, in agreement with reference¹⁸. The aforementioned trade-off between low series resistance and low isolation trenches losses results in larger devices as the number of subcells increases.

Mismatch losses

HM-PVLPCs suffer from mismatch losses if each subcell does not receive the same light power density.^{69,70,71} This situation is likely to occur as a result of the tolerance in the HM-PVLPCs

positioning in the encapsulation and packaging into optical fibre connectors. A theoretical model which takes into account non-uniform illumination, mismatch losses and light spillage was presented⁶⁹ in which the efficiency under mismatched illumination is calculated under the following assumptions:

- The photocurrent is limited by the subcell that receives the lowest optical power.
- Within a partially illuminated subcell, non-uniform illumination causes an increase in some contributions of series resistance, thus decreasing the overall efficiency. This efficiency drop is called “non-uniform illumination losses”.
- The laser beam impinging outside the device active area is lost. This effect is called “spillage losses”.

In order to calculate the efficiency, the degree of misalignment between the laser spot and the device must be specified. Two parameters are used for this purpose: the distance between the device and the spot centres, d , and the angle of misalignment θ (defined as the direction of shift of the beam relative to a given insulation trenches).

The efficiencies obtained are shown in Figure 5c. They mainly depend on d/D_0 , D_0 being the device active area diameter and in a minor extent on θ . As expected, the highest efficiencies are obtained when the laser beam perfectly superposes the device area, i.e. $d/D_0=0$. Afterwards, efficiency rapidly decreases when d/D_0 increases. This efficiency drop is essentially due to light spillage.

Temperature effects

The change in absorption coefficient due to temperature in all subcells is the same. Therefore, temperature variations do not change the current matching between subcells. Consequently, the same behaviour is expected in HM-PVLPC as in S-PVLPCs regarding the influence of temperature on the device efficiency and performance.

Manufacturing process

Except for the need of the thick rear LCL required in HM-PVLPCs, there are no significant differences in the growth of the semiconductor structure with regard to S-PVLPCs. However, the post-growth processing is rather more complex than in S-PVLPCs, with typically twice as many photolithographic steps being required in HM-PVLPCs.⁷²

HM-PVLPC manufacturing consists of the definition of etched areas, metal contacts and interconnects, the formation of dielectric barriers and the deposition of antireflection coatings. A critical step is the series interconnection between subcells. The most commonly used solution is that of the busbar interconnection because it is simpler than others reported, such as air bridges.³⁹ The whole HM-PVLPC manufacture is also greatly determined by the technique used for the dielectric barrier implementation. A thin film of oxide, such as silicon dioxide (SiO_2), silicon nitride (Si_3N_4), etc., can be used for this purpose. Polyimide is an alternative to these materials with several advantages because its processing is fairly simple and it facilitates the subsequent photolithographic steps since polyimide conformably covers the topographical features in the semiconductor surface.^{29, 40}

The highest efficiency achieved by HM-PVLPVs peaks at 55 % at a laser wavelength between 800 and 850 nm⁴⁰.

VERTICAL SERIES CONNECTED PHOTOVOLTAIC LASER POWER CONVERTERS (VM-PVLPCs)

In vertical series-connected photovoltaic laser power converters (VM-PVLPCs) a stack of semiconductor junctions is used^{27,73,74,75}, similarly as in multijunction solar cells. In comparison to HM-PVLPCs, discussed in the previous section, VM-PVLPCs are not affected by areal losses. However, the semiconductor structure used is more complex since it includes tunnel junctions to interconnect the subcells and obviously, a higher number of semiconductor layers. Besides, bottom subcells are subjected to thermal loads during the growth of the rest of the structure, which can complicate the integration of all the subcells and tunnel junctions into a whole VM-PVLPC semiconductor structure.

The design of VM-PVLPCs is also more complicated. Since the different subcells must provide the same photocurrent in order not to lead to current mismatch losses, the thickness of each subcell must be carefully designed. Light is absorbed in the semiconductor structure following the Bouger-Lambert law with an exponential dependence on the semiconductor thickness. So, the thickness of the subcells increases from top to bottom to allow the absorption of the same amount of light per subcell (see Figure 6-left). Because n subcells are vertically interconnected, the voltage of the whole device is roughly N times that of each subcell. Actually, the whole voltage is N -times higher than that of the S-PVLPC minus $N(kT/q)\ln N$, being N the number of subcells and the rest of symbols with their usual meaning) while the current of the whole device is the same as that of a sub-cell (N -times lower than that of the S-PVLPC).

Figure 6: Layer structure of a VM-PVLPC and its efficiency

Sketch of a VM-PVLPC where the thickness of the subcells which are vertically interconnected increases from top to bottom so they provide the same photocurrent. The total thickness of all the subcells allows the absorption of substantially all of the input light (left). **Efficiency vs number of subcells (junctions) and input power (right).** A VM-PVLPCs with an active area of 0.1 cm², an optimized inverted square front grid for each input power and number of subcells with 3 μm wide fingers and sheet resistances of 50 and 0.02 ohm/square for the emitter/window and metal, respectively, and metal/semiconductor contact resistivity of 1·10⁻⁶ Ω·cm². An internal luminescence efficiency of 1 is assumed. For each point the efficiency is maximized by optimizing the number of fingers in the front grid.

One of the main advantages of VM-PVLPCs is the lower influence of non-uniform illumination caused by laser beam misalignment. In VM-PVLPCs, the influence of misalignment is similar to that of S-PVLPCs, since only spillage losses take place and are much lower than in HM-PVLPCs. However, VM-PVLPCs are sensitive to laser wavelength detuning. In the next subsections their design of and the most important effects affecting their performance are discussed.

Design

The most common material used as absorber is GaAs. Solar cells made with this material have already achieved very high photovoltaic conversion efficiencies close to the theoretical limit, featuring internal luminescence efficiencies (η_{int}) approaching 1.^{76,77} In addition, transparent tunnel junctions have also been developed, typically using AlGaAs/GaInP structures,⁷⁸ minimizing the optical and electrical losses in the subcell interconnections. In fact, experimental GaAs-based VM-PVLPCs have also achieved very high power conversion efficiencies over 65% with a number of subcells up to 20.⁴³

The choice of the number of junctions in VM-PVLPCs is determined mostly by the application, i.e., the required output voltage and power. Increasing the number of junctions is required to achieve higher output voltages, as discussed in previous sections. In addition, it helps reducing the series resistance losses as the current in the VM-PVLPCs decreases for higher number of junctions. Figure 6-right shows an illustrative plot of the efficiency vs the number of subcells and input power, for a 0.1 cm² GaAs VM-PVLPC with η_{int} of 1. For a low input power, increasing the number of subcells causes a slight yet significant efficiency drop due to the lower voltage as the subcells current decreases. For high input power, the effect of the series resistance dominates, and higher efficiencies are clearly achieved by raising the number of junctions, more notably as the input power increases. In summary, in absence of series resistance effects, the maximum efficiency is achieved with single-junction VM-PVLPCs (i.e. a S-PVLPC) but 3 or more junctions are required to achieve typical voltages in most applications. If the series resistance effect is significant, for example at high input power densities, using a higher number of junctions can be advisable. Nevertheless, it must be taken into account that VM-PVLPCs are affected by laser wavelength detuning, discussed in the next section.

The highest efficiency in a VM-PVLPCs was reported by Fafard et al.,³¹ with a value of ~70% for an input optical power of 1.5W. In the same work, they reported the performance of VM-PVLPCs with a higher number of junctions up to 12 and higher input powers up to 5.5 W at conversion efficiencies over 50%. Also remarkable is the high output voltage design achieved by the same group with a 20-junction VM-PVLPC delivering a V_{oc} of 23 V and a conversion efficiency of 60% for an input power of 5 W. In all these cases, the performance is significantly affected by the effect of detuning between the laser wavelength used and the VM-PVLPC design, which becomes increasingly complex.

Performance sensitivity to detuning

The high-power laser sources typically used in PBL applications feature spectral widths of just a few nanometers. Therefore, to maximize the efficiency of VM-PVLPCs by achieving current matching, a fine control of the absorber thickness in the upper subcells is required. This is

illustrated in Figure 7-left, which shows the EQE of a GaAs triple junction (3J) VM-PVLPC designed for a laser wavelength of 808 nm. The EQE curves of the three junctions cross at that precise wavelength, which produces the desired current matching. The slope of the curves at that point indicates the sensitivity to laser wavelength detuning: the top and bottom subcells are the most sensitive. This detuning of the laser wavelength can be caused by temperature coefficients or manufacturing tolerances, and can have a large impact on the efficiency of the VM-PVLPC. In Figure 7-right, the variation in the I_{sc} vs the wavelength detuning is shown for VM-PVLPC designed for two laser wavelengths and with different number of junctions. The higher the number of junctions, the higher the sensitivity to laser detuning. Besides, the closer the laser wavelength is to the bandgap of the absorber material (GaAs in this example), the higher the sensitivity too, due to the larger slope of the absorption coefficient as the bandgap wavelength is approached. The sensitivity is also higher for detuning towards lower wavelengths, due to the higher absorption in the upper subcells. The quantitative values obtained are significant, with current losses of up to 15% for a detuning of just 3 nm, which can easily happen in a VCSEL laser source operating at a range of output powers,⁷⁹ in a 10J VM-PVLPCs, and 3% for a 3J VM-PVLPC, indicating that this effect can be one of the main power loss sources in VM-PVLPCs.

Figure 7. Effects of laser detuning on VM-PVLPCs

Left: calculated EQE of a GaAs 3J VM-PVLPC designed for 808 nm laser wavelength. Right: effect of laser wavelength detuning on the I_{sc} of VM-PVLPCs with different number of junctions and designed for two laser wavelengths.

The detuning of the VM-PVLPCs can be caused not only by departures of the laser wavelength from the nominal but also by fabrication tolerances of the PVLPC. Variations in the thicknesses of the subcells absorbers or antireflective coating cause photocurrent imbalances leading to efficiency losses. This effect is again more accentuated for higher number of junctions, since the upper subcells become thinner and their photocurrents are more sensitive to thickness tolerances.

Photon coupling

Photon coupling between junctions in a multijunction solar cell has been extensively studied.⁸⁰ By this effect, the excess photocarriers generated in a junction (subcell), due to spectral mismatches, can be reemitted as photons and transferred to other subcells. In typical multijunction solar cells, the photons are transferred from upper subcells (with higher bandgap) to the lower subcells. For this effect to be significant, the subcells η_{int} must be high and the optical environment must also enable an efficient transfer of photons without internal reflections or parasitic absorption. High quality GaAs VM-PVLPCs with transparent tunnel

junctions meet these requirements. Moreover, since all subcells are made of the same material, the coupling of photons is not restricted to happen from upper to lower subcells, but it occurs between all the subcells, with varying coupling factors. This is illustrated in Figure 8 – left, which shows the luminescence coupling factors between the junctions of a 10J GaAs VM-PVLPC. A number of details influences the combination of coupling factors obtained, but generally speaking, adjacent and thicker junctions exhibit the highest coupling factors. In fact, the highest luminescence coupling factor is attained between the bottom subcells, which are the thickest. The sum of all the coupling factors approaches 1 for $\eta_{\text{int}} = 1$ in all the subcells and if no parasitic photon absorption takes place.

Luminescence coupling has been demonstrated to help mitigate the effect of spectral mismatches in multijunction solar cells.⁸¹ Similarly, it helps alleviate subcell photocurrent imbalances caused by laser wavelength detuning or thickness tolerances in VM-PVLPCs. In fact, the effect of luminescence coupling on GaAs VM-PVLPCs has been shown experimentally to produce a broadening of the EQE response^{82,83} which enhances the resilience of the performance to wavelength detuning.⁸⁴ This is illustrated in Figure 8-right with the calculation for the case of a 10J GaAs VM-PVLPC optimized for 808 nm wavelength and using a laser detuned by -3 nm. The cases of no luminescence coupling, and luminescence coupling assuming a η_{int} of 0.8 and 1 are shown. Without luminescence coupling, a I_{sc} and efficiency loss over 5% and 2.5%, respectively, are obtained. Note that the efficiency loss is lower than the I_{sc} loss because the fill factor increases with the current mismatch. With luminescence coupling, the I_{sc} loss is reduced, and the efficiency even experiences a gain with respect to the tuned laser case. This is due to the gain in V_{oc} , a side effect that has been reported also for multijunction solar cells.^{85,86} For an ideal luminescence coupling, corresponding to an η_{int} of 1, the effect of detuning on the I_{sc} is negligible, and the V_{oc} and efficiency show a gain of over 8% with respect to current matching.

Figure 8. Luminescent coupling between subcells and its effect on VM-PVLPC performance
 Left: coupling factors between junctions in a 10J GaAs VM-PVLPC with a rear gold reflector and $\eta_{\text{int}} = 1$. A lower number in the axis denotes an upper junction and vice versa. Right: influence of luminescence coupling on the effect of laser wavelength detuning on the figures of merit (with respect to current matching case) of a 10J GaAs VM-PVLPC. “LC” refers to luminescence coupling.

Temperature effects

Variations in the temperature change the bandgap of the subcells in the VM-PVLPCs which, similarly as in multijunction cells,⁸⁷ affects the performance of the VM-PVLPC. The effect on the

J_{sc} is of particular importance in VM-PVLPCs, given the fine design necessary to attain current matching in the subcells for narrowband laser beams. A thorough analysis of the effect of temperature on 2J GaAs VM-PVLPCs was reported in,⁸⁸ showing a shift in the current matching wavelength of ~ 15 nm for a temperature variation of ~ 50 °C. This detuning produces a large J_{sc} drop, in addition to the V_{oc} loss due to the lower bandgap caused by the higher temperature. Similar detuning is observed for VM-PVLPC with higher number of subcells, but with a higher J_{sc} loss. Luminescence coupling decreases with temperature due to a lower η_{int} in the GaAs subcells, but this effect decreases with the input power density.⁸⁹ In fact, luminescence coupling has been demonstrated to attenuate the effect of temperature changes on the J_{sc} of VM-PVLPCs for typical operation temperature ranges.^{83,88} In addition, VM-PVLPCs can be designed (optimizing the subcell thicknesses) for a nominal operating temperature, to minimize the power loss due to current mismatch.

In the end, the negative influence of temperature variation in VM-PVLPCs is much higher than in HM-PVLPCs and S-PVLPCs and it can counterbalance the low mismatch losses associated to light misalignment of VM-PVLPCs.

Measurement challenges

Despite VM-PVLPCs are conceptually simple devices, their characterization poses some specific difficulties that do not affect the other PVLPC designs described in previous sections. The most relevant is the complexity of measuring the EQE in devices with a high number of junctions. The measurement of the EQE requires the proper light biasing to separate the contribution of each subcell. This is straightforward in multijunction solar cells, since light sources of the appropriate wavelength can be used for the range of response of each junction. In VM-PVLPCs all the subcells are made of the same material and, therefore, their range of response is the same, although with a different spectral distribution. Finding the appropriate combination of light sources to separate each junction is more problematic as the number of subcells increases. Luminescence coupling only adds complexity to the EQE measurement, as it can interfere in the subcell current balancing. EQE measurements of VM-PVLPCs of up to 3 subcells are feasible (for example using a combination of 500, 720 and 850 nm LED sources, see Figure 13) and have been reported,⁹⁰ but measuring all the subcells in devices with more junctions appears elusive. Without EQE measurements, the current balancing for a given laser source is unknown and hence the analysis of the performance results is hindered. Moreover, the lack of a precisely measured EQE can introduce large errors in the input power calculation if it is done using the I_{sc} produced by the VM-PVLPC and the laser spectrum.⁹¹ Therefore, it is better suited to use a laser beam with controlled and uniform power, with a precise control of the total power actually impinging on the VM-PVLPC area.⁹²

Other challenges such as sample heating or effects of irradiance non uniformities are also important. The effect of temperature was commented above. Irradiance non-uniformities cause, firstly, a higher effective series resistance, which increases with the non-uniformity,⁹³ similarly as in multijunction solar cells.⁹⁴ This, of course, generates ohmic losses. In addition, the peak current of the tunnel junctions can be locally surpassed at some spots of the VM-PVLPC under non-uniform light profiles, causing additional losses. These two effects are reduced as the number of junctions is increased and, therefore, the I_{sc} decreases. Anyway, both heating and non-uniform irradiance effects are not intrinsic to the VM-PVLPCs and can be minimized by

properly engineering the measurement setup. Pulsed measurements can be used to minimize heating, and achieving a uniform light spot is doable using the proper optics.^{27,92}

Manufacturing

The epitaxial growth of the layer structure of VM-PVLPCs is significantly more complex (comprising several tens of layers) than in S-PVLPCs and HM-PVLPCs. Once the semiconductor layer structure has been grown, the manufacturing of the device is similar to S-PVLPCs (including front and back metal contact, device insulation and so on) and much simpler than for HM-PVLPCs. In the end, the fabrication of VM-PVLPCs does not differ significantly from the fabrication of III-V multijunction solar cells. However, tolerances in the thicknesses of the multiple layers that compose the VM-PVLPC, including the semiconductor structure and the ARC, produce much more important conversion efficiency losses than in typical multijunction solar cells. Similarly, as with the effect of detuning of the laser wavelength, the higher the number of junctions, the more important is the impact of fabrication tolerances.

VM-PVLPCs started their development at the beginning of 21st century and they have experienced a significant efficiency increase with a peak efficiency of 66% very close to the current record achieved by S-PVLPC and well over the HM-PVLPCs ones (see Figure 2).

CONCLUSIONS, PERSPECTIVES AND OUTLOOK

Since the first PBL system built in 1978 multitude of applications have been explored and the advantages and enhanced performance of power-by-light solutions have been showcased on a prototype scale. Nevertheless, PBL systems have not become yet a mainstream technology in the numerous industries that could benefit from their advantages. The fact of the matter is that electric utilities, aircraft manufacturers, petrochemical industries and other potential customers have not massively incorporated PBL systems into their equipment and facilities. There might be number of reasons behind this reluctance. Probably, the most obvious is that many applications that PBL systems could potentially serve are critical and thus any technological change demands a thorough demonstration of the maturity, reliability, and durability of the new proposal as well as the existence of a solid supply chain. Some of these challenges have been solved in recent years, at least partially. In terms of technological maturity, efficiencies are now getting close to the theoretical limits revealing a firm understanding of the device physics. However, there still exists a certain typology zoo in PVLPC design (as we have shown in previous sections), which is sometimes interpreted as lack of technological maturity. We will further comment on this below. In terms of the supply chain, we have today a tier-1 semiconductor company –Broadcom Ltd– and a cohort of small start-ups manufacturing PVLPCs of diverse architectures, which ensures the availability of off-the-shelf products for fabricating PBL systems in the long term. Finally, in regard to reliability and durability, PVLPCs have inherited the strong legacy of III-V solar cells used in space and terrestrial concentrator applications. Despite this represents a notable asset, specific reliability studies in PBL systems need to be undertaken to provide a specific piece of evidence in this context.

We believe that the massive deployment of PVLPCs will be led by the VM-PVLPCs since their manufacturing process is very similar to that of III-V multijunction solar cells exhibiting a consolidated track record in reliability and cost reduction. Moreover, VM-PVLPCs are able to reliably supply up to ~10 V with efficiencies over 60% under laser power densities of several

W/cm². Even more, we have described the ways to attain efficiencies over 70% for which an effective luminescent coupling among the subcells is required.

In parallel, S-PVLPCs, which currently have the highest photovoltaic conversion efficiency – namely 68.9%–, can be used as a benchmark to test advanced concepts such as high performance back reflectors, optical confinement, photon recycling, etc. The target is to attain luminescence efficiencies close to unity or, in other words, to reach an operation as close as possible to the radiative limit. Most of these advances can be readily implemented in VM-PVLPCs to further increase their performance.

HM-PVLPCs, because of the complexity of their post-growth process, do not result in efficiencies higher than those of VM-PVLPCs. Therefore, we believe they will not play a key role in PBL technology in the short-term. Nevertheless, their low sensitivity to temperature variations can give them a window of opportunity in certain niche applications. Similarly, hybrid typologies which combine an HM-PVLPC and a VM-PVLPC in the same device, could find some niche applications thanks to their good performance against misalignment and temperature variations despite their manufacturing process is complex and expensive.

PVLPCs are made of III-V semiconductors so they can take advantage of the continuous improvements in material technology and device design developed by the optoelectronic industry. The opportunities and market applications are huge and with the experience gained with the deployment of PVLPCs for the first transmission window, PVLPCs for the second and third optical fibre transmission windows can subsequently evolve. In the end, a constellation of new avenues is waiting for PBL systems to cover a massive number of applications present in our daily life.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors researched data, contributed to the discussion of content and writing and editing of the article prior to submission

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests

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